

distinct rice-free dry season. The extreme variations in rainfall and growing season profoundly affect rice insect pests. The fact that rice fields are flooded during part of the growing season eliminates many soil-inhabiting pests common to dryland environments.

A survey of rice entomologists in eight Asian countries yielded a list of insect pests common to rainfed wetland environments in the region. Most

important were yellow rice borer, rice gall midge, rice leaf folder, rice bug, and rice caseworm, which are also major pests of irrigated wetland environments, but, with the exception of rice bug and rice leaf folder, not of dryland environments. Thirty other pest species were important on a country-to-country basis.

Because of the locational intermingling of rainfed and irrigated environments, it is difficult to state that a pest is

indigenous to rainfed wetland environments. For example, the brown planthopper is capable of migrating long distances and may disperse to rainfed environments from nearby irrigated areas.

Only two pests are thought to be unique to rainfed wetland environments — the rice root weevil and white stem borer. These insects normally estivate and are culturally controlled if a second rice crop is grown in the dry season. ■

Evaluation of granular insecticides for rainfed wetland rice in the Philippines

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Rainfed wetland rice is subject to both drought and flooding. In the Philippines, these extreme conditions influence the performance of insecticides used in controlling the key vegetative pests: whorl maggot, caseworm, and stem borer. Against this insect complex, foliar sprays are inferior to granular insecticide formulations because:

1. Frequent and heavy rainfall reduces the residual activity of sprays, and the need to reapply the sprays makes this form of protection more costly,
2. Larvae of the whorl maggot and stem borer are sheltered within young plants, which protect them from foliar sprays, and
3. Rainfed farmers do not have ready access to water for sprayers.

During the 1977–78 crop year we evaluated the granular insecticides lindane, diazinon, and carbofuran, which are currently recommended in the Philippines for irrigated rice against the early-season pest complex in rainfed wetland paddies.

Diazinon and lindane granules were broadcast at 1.5 kg a.i./ha 3 days after transplanting. Carbofuran granules were incorporated into the soil at 1.0 kg a.i./ha during the last harrowing before transplanting. Previous studies have shown that soil incorporation of carbofuran was superior to broadcasting into the paddy water after transplanting.

The first trial, replicated over five farms planted to IR28, compared lindane

Comparison of carbofuran, lindane, and diazinon granules for whorl maggot and caseworm control on IR28 and IR36.^a Pangasinan, Philippines, 1977–78.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot ^b damage 30 DT	Caseworm (% defoliation) 25 DT	Yield (t/ha)
<i>IR28</i>			
Carbofuran ^c	1 a	2 a	4.67 a
Lindane ^d	8 b	16 b	3.54 b
Untreated	9 b	23 b	3.48 b
<i>IR36</i>			
Carbofuran ^c	1 a	3 a	4.43 a
Diazinon ^d	7 b	11 b	3.99 b
Untreated	8 c	15 c	3.86 b

^aIR28 — av of 5 fields, IR36 — av of 7 fields. DT = days after transplanting. In a column any 2 means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b1–9 scale: 1 = negligible, 9 = severe. ^c1.0 kg a.i./ha, soil incorporated. ^d1.5 kg a.i./ha, broadcast at 3 DT.

to carbofuran. Lindane was totally ineffective against the whorl maggot and caseworm, but carbofuran controlled both pests adequately and produced significant yield increases (see table).

The second trial, replicated over seven farms planted to IR36, compared diazinon to carbofuran. Diazinon reduced whorl maggot and caseworm infestation only slightly — not enough to significantly increase yield. But carbofuran again gave excellent control and significantly higher yields.

We believe that the failure of both lindane and diazinon granules was due to the shallow paddy water, which characterizes rainfed wetland fields. We monitored the water depth daily for 30 days after transplanting. The mean depth per field ranged from 1.0 to 5.8 cm. Neither insecticide is truly systemic. Once applied to the fields the insecticides move up the plants in the capillary film between the leaf sheath and the culm. The degree of movement depends on the depth of the paddy water. In rainfed

areas the paddy water is normally too shallow to allow adequate movement up the plants. Therefore lindane and diazinon should not be recommended if the paddy water levels cannot be adequately maintained. ■

A new record of the cricket *Euscyrtus concinnus* Hanu (Eneopterinae)

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A number of field crickets (Gryllidae) and several grasshoppers defoliate the paddy crop. The gryllids reported on paddy are *Brachytrupes portentosus* Licht, *Gryllus conspersus* Schaum., *Liogryllus bimaculatus* de Geer., and *Trigonidium cicindeloides* Serv.

A new cricket has been found feeding on paddy leaves at the Instructional Farm, College of Agriculture, Vellayani. The Zoological Survey of India identified it as *Euscyrtus concinnus* Hanu.

Both nymphs and adults feed on the

leaves. Although all crop stages are susceptible, the infestation rate and feeding are heavier in nurseries about to be transplanted and in the early transplanted crop. During heavy incidence, almost all leaves are infested. Feeding symptoms are narrow linear holes in the interveinal areas that leave the veins intact. Such holes are

distributed along the entire leaf lamina and resemble those made by grasshoppers.

A field trial was conducted to determine suitable insecticides for controlling crickets as well as other insects. Six insecticide granules were tried at 2 levels:

- Carbofuran at 0.5 kg and 1.0 kg a.i./ha
- Phorate at 1.0 kg and 2.0 kg a.i./ha

- Mephosfolan at 0.5 kg and 1.0 kg a.i./ha
- Disulfoton at 1.0 kg and 2.0 kg a.i./ha
- Quinalphos at 1.0 kg and 2.0 kg a.i./ha
- Chlordimeform hydrochloride at 0.5 kg and 1.0 kg a.i./ha.

Of these carbofuran at 1.0 kg a.i./ha was the most effective in pest control, followed by phorate at 2.0 kg a.i./ha. ■

Occurrence of the rice ear-cutting caterpillar in the Punjab of Pakistan

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The rice ear-cutting caterpillar *Pseudaletia unipuncta* has never been a serious rice pest in the Punjab Province of Pakistan. The first observation of serious damage was reported on berseem fodder (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) in 1972. That crop is sown after rice harvest in the rice tract of Pakistan. At that time only a few larvae and pupae are observed in rice stubble. An unusual upsurge of the pest was noticed in the area of the Institute in October and November. Attacks of the pest were also recorded in Narang and Kamoke areas (Sheikhupura District). The pest attacked the rice crop when routine insecticide applications were halted after the third week of September.

Observations of ear-cutting caterpillars, Punjab, Pakistan.

Variety	Visual assessment of damaged panicles (%)	Insects (av no./hill)
BR2360-6-5-1-10	95	5.4
BR51-46-5	90	4.6
IET6073	70	1.8
BP919-24-7-1	50	2.2
B541-B-KN-22-7-2	30	3.0
B441-B-126-3-2-1	15	1.2
B541-B-KN58-5-3	10	1.6
IET3363	5	1.4

The larvae damaged some varieties considerably. The insect preferred semidwarf varieties, particularly those that were relatively green. Panicles of such varieties were completely denuded.

Observations on the number of insects per hill were recorded in a field sown to different varieties. Five hills per sample were checked. The results are in the table.

From 1.2 to 5.4 insects/hill, averaging

2.6/hill. were present (see table). As expected, varieties with more insects were damaged more; the soil surface was completely covered with cut panicles and grains.

In a preliminary trial, dusting the crop with a mixture of BHC (0.25 kg a.i./ha) + DDT (0.75 kg a.i./ha) killed 95% of the larvae within 24 hours of the application. Water was completely drained before dusting. ■

Two subterranean pests of upland rice in Papua New Guinea

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Two rice pests newly identified in Papua New Guinea can severely damage upland rice in the seedling and tillering stages.

Infestation symptoms are similar to those of kresek, a systemic symptom caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae*. Seedlings that are attacked at an early age die, and more mature plants that are attacked have fewer tillers and fewer spikelets per panicle. The younger tillers are affected most severely. Widespread infestation

can destroy as much as 90% of the crop.

Caenoblyssus pilosus (Hemiptera: Lygaeidae), a chinch bug previously reported from the western Carolines, is related to *Blissus* sp., a pest of maize, small grains, and turf grasses.

In appearance and life cycle it is similar to *Blissus* sp. At the youngest stage it is 0.7 mm long. At adult stage, the insect is about 3 mm long, with silver wings on a black body. At the juvenile stage it is red with black markings.

Chinch bugs inhabit the root zone immediately adjacent to the base of the plant within 1 or 2 cm of the soil surface. They may be visible on the soil surface in the early morning or late afternoon.

Mealy bugs (family Pseudococcidae)

have also been observed in most fields that are attacked by chinch bugs. They are often found on nearby plants, but not on the same plants as chinch bugs. Ants, which tend the mealy bugs, are usually present on the soil surface at the base of the plant.

The adult mealy bug is 2.5 cm long and off-white to pink. Both the chinch bug and the mealy bug damage the plant by extracting moisture and nutrients from the roots. They also attack maize and sorghum, but because the infestation level is lower, damage symptoms are not visible.

Puspalum sp. and other soft-stemmed grasses are alternate hosts of the chinch bug.